

Proposed Communitized Digital Marketing Strategies to Enhance Brand Awareness for Cafe in Tangerang (Study Case: El Primero Cafe & Meet)

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ABSTRACT: The background of this research is the anxiety of one of the Cafe owners in Tangerang, El Primero Cafe & Meet, who has experienced an inconsistency in the number of visitors. This problem shows that the existence of El Primero Cafe & Meet has not been very visible to the market, one of which is its digital presence which greatly provides opportunities for businesses to be seen by the market on a global scale. With a minimal digital presence, El Primero Cafe & Meet is difficult to achieve high brand awareness. One solution that can be done is to focus on planning a digital marketing strategy so that digital activities are consistent, have targets, and can be used as a source of market research data for business development. In addition, in the collaborative and digital era, of course, involving the community directly with brands can be an interesting strategy to adopt. By combining the digital world and the concept of communitization, El Primero can form a close relationship with the online market and community and introduce their place as "Home" for collaborating communities. The purpose of this research is to develop a community-based digital marketing strategy to increase brand awareness of El Primero Cafe & Meet.

This study used a qualitative method by conducting interviews with 3 categories of informants; management, community, and general consumers with a total of 8 interviewees. The core idea of each interview is to explore the behavior of the market towards the digital world, what digital marketing concepts are needed by the market, to management's expectations regarding the strategy to be designed. From the research results, data was obtained in the form of consumer behavior in accessing digital platforms on a daily basis on the digital platform channels. These data are then processed into thought concepts in the preparation of a digital marketing strategy with SOSTAC Framework and this strategy will be used to increase brand awareness of El Primero Cafe & Meet in the next 6 months as a pilot stage.

KEYWORDS: Communitization, Digital marketing, F&B Business, SOSTAC Framework.

A. INTRODUCTION

The food and beverage industry is one of the driving industries for the economy in a country, one of which is Indonesia. With high consumption and the number of Indonesian people reaching 275,361,267 people, this industry will never be paralyzed even after experiencing a crisis in the era of the pandemic. Figure I show us about the progressive path of F&B Industry in Indonesia. As we can see, in 2021, If measured by GDP at constant prices (ADHK) 2010, the food and beverage industry grew 2.54% to Rp775.1 trillion last year compared to the previous year. However, the problem that often occurs is how the process of developing the F&B business is so that it grows both from brand awareness and the profit that can be generated. Brand awareness itself is how a customer has the ability to put the brand at the top of the mind because the existence of the brand is very influential for the customer. Additionally, it is believed that brand awareness is a requirement for brands to be taken into account by customers throughout the decision-making process [1].

Figure I. Food and Beverage Industry Value and GDP Growth (2010-2021)

In the F&B business, brand awareness can be created in various ways. From product uniqueness to broad, creative, and flexible marketing methods. So, when customers think about consuming a food or drink, they will easily decide to choose an F&B brand with high brand awareness. The ease with which customers decide which brand to buy among the many F&B businesses is certainly an important factor for the growth of the F&B business. Digital marketing, the most nowadays promising method to increase brand awareness can be the answer for F&B business. The reason is that today's customers consider a lot what they will consume from digital platforms, both social media and digital advertising on other platforms. The attractiveness of the content and the high intensity of digital marketing will generate interest and high brand recall from customers. It's possible that exposure to amusing brand media like videos, images, and stories might increase brand recall and brand identification [2]. The other things to achieve high brand awareness, many brands use a marketing system that relies on differences in targeting from individuals to more on similarities to several individuals who can be categorized as communities. Individuals may optimize their social capital by using a variety of methods, including brand communities, to form and cultivate social interactions and so increase their social capital. Perceived connections between the client, their product, the brand, the business, and other owners make up what we call "integration" in the brand community. Communities dedicated to a certain brand may be located everywhere, not just online. The medium of human communication may range from face-to-face encounters to technological technologies [3]

El Primero Cafe & Meet, one of the cafes that has been around for a long time (together with the "Kampung Sepeda" community in the South Tangerang area) has potential but until now it still doesn't have a clear direction and digital strategy to increase brand awareness. The owner of El Primero Cafe & Meet is reviewing whether his decision to increase the supply of raw materials and investment in assets for the feasibility of the outlet if it is opened to the public is a bad decision or not. The reason is, After running and being opened to the public for 8 months, the number of visitors who attended did not match their expectations (Figure II shows the number of arrivals at El Primero Cafe & Meet since it was opened to the public).

Figure II. El Primero Visitors Number

To analyze what are the real sources of the problems they are experiencing, we can analysis using Root Cause Analysis (RCA). Using this RCA, there are a lot of method/tools we can use in many situations, including the problem suffered by owner of El Primero Cafe & Meet. Of the many tools that can be used to perform RCA, one of the most effective and efficient for all problems is Cause-Effect Mapping [4].

Figure III. Cause-Map Diagram of the problem

Based on the exploration of the problems shown in Figure III, we can see that this business not in the right way because they brand awareness was very low and they don't have the strategic plan of digital marketing to boost it. Because of lack presence from this brand in digital platform, it cause the small and inconsistent amount of visitors come and buy. From all this problem, we can determine that the root cause of this problem is the absence of a strategic digital marketing plan. The main target of digital marketing is to make as much as customer to come to El Primero and have experience the great ambience and products right here. Supported by the great digital communication, presence, and marketing, it will make the brand awareness from individual and communities

formed. The root cause diagram also tell us about El Primero need to adjust their digital presence to be better and go forward running their business publicly rather than go back to their business previous concept (cafe just for their bike shop client or owner’s business partner). Of course, the marketing division as the division that is responsible to the owner needs to provide solutions so that this problem can be solved progressively (in a long term).

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing is a dynamic, ever-evolving, and restless corporate activity. Due to the quick development of new technology, the function of marketing has also altered significantly. A formalized method of gathering precise and timely information about customers, products, the marketplace, and the overall environment is now necessary due to such changes, including the internet, which have forced today's marketing executive to become more market driven in their strategic decision making. Nowadays, marketing is not only done conventionally like marketing practices a few years ago. Even though this method is still often used, business people need to look at technological developments and customers' habits to use technology as their decision making in buying a product or using a service. Digital marketing is the use of digital technology to assist in marketing efforts so as to increase consumer understanding by better matching their demands [5]. Digital marketing is not just conventional marketing with digital features added. It has unique qualities and dynamics that must be comprehended in order to adopt efficient marketing approaches and strategies. Digital channels may be categorized in a number of ways. One method of categorizing the channels is to categorize them depending on who controls the communications (the firm or the target audience) and whether the communications are one-way or two-way [6]. One-way communication on digital channels can be defined as communication method from company to market and its done. The general purpose of this communication is to inform some information that can attract market without any open discussion that involving the market. Two-way communication in digital marketing that is most popular and successful in the current era is social media and community formation from companies to their brands. Due to the interactive nature of social media, marketing campaigns must be framed as conversations between the firm and its consumers, rather than one-way communications. Obviously, the firm has less say over the brand's representation in social media. Social media users aren't looking to be pitched, but rather informed, by the discussions around a brand [7]. All the one-way communication and two-way communication combine for the marketing channels will lead brands into perfect marketing communication phase. By optimizing this complete channels, it will generate high brand awareness for early stage and make a promising relationship with customer. The good relationship will make the “free marketing” as well when customer get their easiness to know and satisfied by how the brand communicate to them. Figure IV summarizes the digital marketing channels that can utilize nowadays.

	High company control	Low company control
One-way	Website E-mail newsletters Online directories Banner adverting	SEO (Search engine optimization) SEA (Search engine advertising)
Two-way	Company generated blogs Company's own communities	Social media

Figure IV. Digital marketing Channels

Another factor that is a pillar for the preparation of a digital marketing is how a business can understand the needs and behavior of their customers. To get them interested in coming somewhere, of course marketers need to know the behavior of the market from various aspects. How does the market live daily on digital platforms, how do they consider whether they should come to that place, to find out their views on their favorite places to visit. One way to analyze is to do a customer analysis. Customer Analysis is a crucial component of any business strategy, regardless of its stage of growth. Customer profiles may be built for your whole customer base or for particular groups in which your organization is interested, such as high-value consumers, those who are purchasing a new product or service, and those who are more inclined to purchase online as opposed to in-store. To achieve success, the customer profiling procedure should take into consideration the broadest possible range of client data pertaining to four essential

consumer attributes. A customer profile is a complete description of your present consumers based on their demographic information, geographic location, buying habits, or propensity to utilize certain goods and channels. Table I summarizes the definitions of what customer profile information needed for complete data [8]

Table I. Customer Profiling and Analysis Characteristics

Customer Analysis Key Characteristics			
Customer Demographics	Market Insights	Customer Behavior	Customer Buying Journey
Customers' locations, ages, genders, family incomes, presence and ages of children, as well as supplementary information such as channel and brand use preferences.	Customers' behavior outside of the organization, including the channels they typically utilize, their brand preferences, and the items and services they are likely to purchase.	How consumers connect with your organization, including how often they interact and which items they purchase.	How consumers connect with your channels, including which channels they use, whether they are online or offline, their acquisition source, and their email preferences and interactions.

○ **Communitization Concept**

The concept of forming a community by a brand is now very widely used. Brands can position themselves no longer above consumers, but on equal footing or even collaborating with consumers. Brands listen more to what the community wants as input for the development of their products or services. Thus, there will be harmonization between the two parties to form an efficient business system. Of course, in the process of establishing a good community environment for the process of creating a brand community, there are several aspects that need to be modified, one of which is the basic marketing concept (segmentation, targeting, positioning, marketing mix). There are nine essential marketing components, including segmentation, targeting, positioning, differentiation, marketing, selling, brand, service, and process [9]. This marketing transformation is known as new wave marketing.

Table II. New Wave Marketing Transformation Concept

New Wave Marketing Component	Legacy Marketing Elements	New Wave Marketing Elements
Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Segmentation Targeting Positioning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communitization Confirmation Clarification
Tactic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Differentiation Marketing Mix: (product, price, place & promotion) Selling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Condification (co-creation, currency, communal activation & conversation) Commercialization
Value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brand Service Process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Character Care Collaboration

In a more particular context, communitization is one of the key components of new wave marketing, which substitutes traditional segmentation with a broader focus. In Legacy Marketing, firms see consumers as the promotion's intended audience (therefore a vertical connection), but in New Wave Marketing, customers and marketers are on an equal footing. Companies design

Communitization, cultivate and cultivate their engagement with them (therefore horizontal relationship). After its development, the consumers will get acquainted.

C. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

On research methodology explains that in compiling a digital marketing strategy for El Primero Cafe & Meet, it is necessary to explore existing problems based on available facts and data. Starting from how El Primero determines the issue, this research moves with an exploration of the current situation and the problems experienced by the brand. After that, it is necessary to explore the factors that are the key to making decisions in preparing digital marketing strategies for every data needed to support the drafting process. After the data is collected, then this research will move towards analysis and drawing conclusions that will be compiled in the digital marketing implementation plan for El Primero. These data are used as secondary data to support primary data which will be collected based on interview. The combination of these data will become the basis for the formulation of a digital marketing strategy supported by theories that can be used and are relevant to the cases experienced by El Primero Cafe & Meet.

○ **Data Collection**

An interview is designed to capture and analyze people's thoughts, feelings, and views about pertinent issues. The replies must provide more thorough information. Comparatively speaking, this provides a better understanding of social issues than quantitative tools like surveys and questionnaires. Additionally, interviews are useful for gathering information when a study examines more delicate issues that participants might not feel entirely at ease discussing in a group setting. In contrast to a structured interview, a semi-structured interview is more flexible and allows the interviewer or the subject to veer off topic if more exploration of an issue is desired. The researcher begins a semi-structured interview with a basic outline of themes that may be built upon as necessary. The inquiries can be put to various participants in various ways while keeping in mind the intended context [10]. Based on table III, the researcher will conduct interviews with 8 respondents consisting of El Primero Cafe & Meet owners, outlet managers, marketing division supervisors, 2 representatives from the community as customers, and 3 random customers from mixed profile (different ages, work status, etc). The purpose of interviewing each respondent is to have several questions that lead to the same core, but of course by extracting information from different perspectives depending on the data you want to get.

Table III. Interview Design

Interviewee	Respondent Profile	Big Questions to Discuss	Interview Method
Owner of El Primero Cafe & Meet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Name : Tjandra ● Age : 48 years old ● Sex : Male ● Job Description : Businessman, CEO ● Industry : Bicycle, F&B ● Experiences : 26 years 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How important is brand awareness for coffee shops? 2. How do you asses the brand awareness and digital marketing of El Primero now? (scope of area, market profile, digital presence) 	Semi-structured interview
Outlet manager of El Primero Cafe & Meet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Name : Ihsan ● Age : 26 years old ● Sex : Male ● Job Description : F&B Supervisor, Manager ● Industry : F&B ● Experiences : 4 years 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. What are your goals or expectations regarding to digital marketing performance? (after the new strategy planned) 	Semi-structured interview

Marketing supervisor of El Primero Cafe & Meet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Name : Jennie ● Age : 24 years old ● Sex : Female ● Job Description : Marketing Supervisor ● Industry : F&B, Fashion ● Experiences : 2 years 		Semi-structured interview
2 Representatives of community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Name : Den ● Age : 28 years old ● Sex : Male ● Job Description : Coffee Roaster ● Industry : Coffee ● Experiences : 5 years ● Name : Valdi ● Age : 26 years old ● Sex : Male ● Job Description : Content Creator ● Industry : Fashion, Coffee, Creative ● Experiences : 4 years 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. What is the biggest consideration to come to coffee shop? 5. What makes community attracted to do activity in coffee shops? 6. Where do you mostly search information about coffee shops? 7. What kind of digital marketing that mostly affect the decision to come? 	Semi-structured interview
3 Representatives of general customer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Name : Sugiarto ● Age : 41 years old ● Sex : Male ● Job Description : Corporate Employee ● Industry : Finance ● Experiences : 12 years ● Name : Icha ● Age : 22 years old ● Sex : Female ● Job Description : College Student ● Industry : - ● Experiences : - ● Name : Adrian ● Age : 29 years old ● Sex : Male ● Job Description : Entrepreneur 		Semi-structured interview

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry : Fashion • Experiences : 3 years 		
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The secondary data will be collected by internal data (served by management of El Primero Cafe & Meet in several aspects agreement), Journal and articles. Internal data will provide facts regarding the condition of El Primero Cafe & Meet in the current period. With internal data, researchers can see and assess how appropriate steps to anticipate problems that occur. Internal data has high credibility because it is provided directly by the research source. Internal data will be supported by a compilation of theories and data that can be retrieved from several journals and articles. Journals and articles used must have high relevance and credibility (sources, citations with high scores, and good ratings).

- **Data Analysis**
 1. Coding Analysis where in this process we determine the code for each sentence. Determination of the code based on the topic of the sentence generated from the interview session.
 2. SWOT Analysis, The SWOT Analysis is a realistic, fact-based, data-driven examination of a company's relative strengths and weaknesses. Before settling on a new course of action, a business might do a SWOT Analysis to evaluate its current situation
 3. SOSTAC Framework, SOSTAC Framework, A framework for the planning process that helps organize and manage plan execution. Situation, Objectives, Strategy, Tactics, and Control is an acronym that was invented by PR Smith for marketing communications planning.

D. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

○ **Interview Results**

Interview sessions packaged with a semi-structured interview system were conducted with 8 interviewees who represented important elements in extracting information and points of view to develop a digital marketing strategy. Interviews were conducted with 3 management people, namely the owner of El Primero Cafe & Meet, the outlet manager and also the marketing supervisor. These three people became the target respondents to find their point of view about this brand from an internal side, assess the condition of this digital marketing brand and their expectations after this strategy was designed and implemented. Another interview was conducted with 5 people who were classified as customers from two customer categories, community representatives and general customers. Keep in mind that El Primero Cafe & Meet's target market prioritizes communities to form a collaborative and active community environment at this outlet. Thus, the point of view of community representatives will be important information about what the community really wants from the place they will make their "home" in their activities with other communities. As a customer category that is also covered by general customers, other important information that needs to be known is how the market behaves, where do they usually dig for information about cafes or places they want to visit, and what are their considerations for coming to the cafe. All this information will be the mixed and synthesized information as a foundation for making the digital marketing strategy. Based on the results of interviews with management, there is one quite interesting point where the three respondents have the same mindset, namely awareness of a brand is the main key to running a business. Of course, a business, especially in the F&B industry, needs to "tempt" customers with their uniqueness so that the market wants to be here. These three sources also agree that they have always been open to the public and have not focused on digital marketing in their marketing system. This is the core of the problem that can be exploited as an opportunity. Researchers analyzed the activities of El Primero's official Instagram that there is still a lot of optimization they can do. Starting from the packaging of content, the flow of information on the page, to advertising activities that they haven't done yet. With inconsistent activity and opportunities for more massive performance, of course this condition is not good, especially since El Primero only has Instagram as a channel. Another interesting thing is what was conveyed by Jennie regarding what type of communication they usually apply on Instagram. Social media is the best two-way communication platform in the current era. With social media, a brand can be with the market rather than being above the market. Thus, closeness between customers and brands can be created.

The next results are the results of interviews with 5 customers who are categorized into 2, namely community representatives and general end customers. Based on the results of interviews with two community representatives, researchers learned that the needs

of each community in those who are active and involved with El Primero are how El Primero can in the future provide "special treatment" and facilities such as an internet connection and a large area. It is essential for a cafe to express to the market, through a digital platform, that their establishment provides the facilities necessary to fulfill market needs. This information must be communicated clearly. "Easiness to take a content" said Valdi as a content creator of lifestyle means something interesting to communicate. For community that makes content everytime, the flexibility for them without scare about rules of using camera need to be communicate by outlet. More contents made by communities, it's a big opportunity for brand to expand their brand awareness. Based on all the interview conducted, Researchers obtain information that can be used as a consideration in analyzing the state of digital marketing and preparing digital marketing strategies at El Primero.

o **Solution and Implementation Plan**

To process the results of the insights from the interviewees, researchers used the SOSTAC Framework to synthesize digital marketing strategies as the goal of this study. This framework is very strategic to use because it is based on a process that has a complete flow starting from situation analysis to how we control the results that will obtained after the strategy implemented.

Figure VI. SOSTAC Framework

1. *Situation analysis*

Table IV. SWOT Analysis of El Primero’s Digital Marketing

Strength	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Already have followers from Instagram and online relationship from internal to their friends - Great quality of content in Instagram (ambience, menu) - Have good technologies and many human from internal resources - Fast response admin on Instagram 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Only use one platform and channels to do digital marketing - Lack of digital marketing experience from marketing staffs - Low intensity of digital presence (on instagram) - Unclear online market targeting - Lack of communitiy-based online marketing communication

Opportunity	Threat
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Market behavior with high intensity on accessing digital platform and social media - The rising number of community with “collaboration” principle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Great performance of competitor’s digital marketing - Fast-forward digital trend stream

Based on the SWOT analysis above, it can be assessed that there are several points that El Primero needs to pay attention to so that he can increase brand awareness in the online world through optimal digital marketing activities. This SWOT analysis can produce a strategy that is suitable for El Primero's internal and external conditions by using the TOWS Cross-Matrix

2. *Objective settings*

In determining the objectives of digital marketing activities, we need to see how the company wants and matches market needs. we can see that of course the main goal is to achieve a higher level of brand awareness on digital platforms. High brand awareness will increase the number of visitors so that there is a flow of recommendations between visitors who keep coming to El Primero. To breakdown the main goal of digital marketing strategies, we can use SMART Framework on structuring the objectives. The acronym SMART refers to Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, and Time-Bound objectives. The First objective is Increase the number of interactions (following or contacting the platform) digital pages of the El Primero platform by 30% every month for the next 6 months. This objective will be achieved by launching and optimizing 3 digital platforms as digital marketing implementation channels, Tiktok, Whatsapp and existing Instagram until February 2023 and execute digital marketing activities in the next 4 months. This can be an opportunity because existing followers and customers from El Primero are intense in accessing all three digital platforms as their daily routine. Thus, increasing the number of interactions will increase brand awareness. The second objective is to Build and involve relationships with 5 communities every month for 2023. Building relationships can be done by actively conducting outbound marketing through various social media platforms such as Tiktok, Instagram and Whatsapp. Marketing content can be in the form of special offers so that the community is interested in coming to El Primero and collaborating with other communities to form a communal climate in El Primero.

After researcher analyze the situation and set the objectives, then the next step is to set the communitized digital marketing Strategies and Tactics. On this phase, researcher will combine all the current situation of digital marketing and also the objectives expected to synthesize the detail part of strategies can be applied based on several factors. After that, the last phases are Action and Control phase which is needed for El Primero to execute the strategies and monitor it for data and evaluation.

3. *Strategy and Tactics*

The SOSTAC strategy phase developed the tactics by referencing the previously specified goals. The objective of mapping causes and effects in the strategy creation process is to achieve strategic alignment with the strategic goals of the firm. This phase is developed from SWOT analysis in situation analysis, transform into TOWS Cross-Matrix and the develop more detail in the RACE Planning steps, which include (1)target and segmentation, (2)positioning, (3)proposition and marketing mix, (4)brand strategy, (5)online representation, (6)content and engagement strategy, (7)digital channel acquisition communication strategy, (8)digital conversion channel strategy, (9)digital channel retention communication strategy, (10)data strategy, (11)multi- channel integration strategy, and (12)social media strategy.

Table V. TOWS Cross-Matrix of El Primero’s Digital Marketing

	Strength	Weakness
	<p>S1. Already have followers from Instagram and online relationship from internal to their friends</p>	<p>W1. Only use one platform and channels to do digital marketing</p> <p>W2. Lack of digital marketing experience</p>

	<p>S2. Great quality of content on Instagram (ambience, menu)</p> <p>S3. Have good technologies and many human from internal resources</p> <p>S4. Fast response admin on Instagram</p>	<p>from marketing staffs</p> <p>W3. Low intensity of digital presence (on instagram)</p> <p>W4. Unclear online market targeting</p> <p>W5. Lack of community-based online marketing communication</p>
<p>Opportunity</p> <p>O1. Market behavior with high intensity on accessing digital platform and social media</p> <p>O2. The rising number of community with “collaboration” principle</p>	<p>S-O Strategies</p> <p>SO1. Appoint one digital marketer from staff to take a charge directly in digital marketing activities</p> <p>SO2. Make a great quality and relate content to market for all platform</p> <p>SO3. Optimize digital communication and database</p>	<p>W-O Strategies</p> <p>WO1. Launch another digital platform favors by market</p> <p>WO2. Collaborate with communities and influencers</p> <p>WO3. Do some campaign and outbound marketing related to customer profile</p>
<p>Threat</p> <p>T1. Great performance of competitor’s digital marketing</p> <p>T2. Fast-forward digital trend stream</p>	<p>S-T Strategies</p> <p>ST1. Maintain competitor activities with internet benchmarking</p> <p>ST2. Routine meeting for brainstorming the new idea of digital marketing trends</p>	<p>W-T Strategies</p> <p>WT1. Consistent and target oriented digital activities execution</p> <p>WT.2 Optimize digital communication</p> <p>WT3. Human resource training or hire new digital marketer for better digital marketing performance</p>

From the several strategies above that have been produced, researchers take several strategies that priority to execute for El primero Cafe & Meet issue and make more details in the form of several tactics in the execution of these strategies

Table VI. Strategy and Tactic Formulation of El Primeros’s Digital Marketing

Strategy	References of Strategy (From RACE Planning)	Tactic(s)
Make a great quality and relate content to market for all platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Content and engagement strategy - Social media marketing strategy - Multichannel integration strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make content pillars in every digital platform that typical in each of them but still relate each other - UGC content type - Monthly content plan to monitor the process, quality, and target.
Optimize digital Communication and database	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital channel acquisition communication strategy - Social media marketing strategy - Multichannel integration strategy - Data strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimize SEO - Optimize branding message and communication in social media - Build authentic communication to market in every platform media

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make multichannel links to bind all platform
Launch another digital platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Brand strategy - Online representation - Digital channel retention communication strategy - Social media marketing strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Launch Tiktok for video-based content with light topics related to brand - Introduce Whatsapp for outbound marketing - Optimize all the platform in professional form
Collaborate with communities and influencers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Target and segmentation - Online representation - Social media marketing strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Approach many kind segment of communities such as fashion, coffee, lifestyle, even entertainment - List down all influencers that match with El Primero target market - Make collaboration timeline in every month to maintain the relation and awareness effect - Make special discount for communities in every time they involved with El Primero
Do some campaign and outbound marketing related to customer profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Content and engagement strategy - Digital channel acquisition communication strategy - Digital conversion channel strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select strategic special offer to be campaign for online market - Contact customer WhatsApp after their first visit - Launch digital ads - Collect and utilize customer data
Consistent and target oriented digital activities execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Brand strategy - Online representation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weekly and monthly meeting for digital marketing performance monitoring and evaluation - Make timeline with PIC in execute all digital marketing activities

4. *Actions and Control*

The action segment discusses how a brand can execute each tactic in detail. Each action taken must be specific and measurable, where this measurable aspect will be considered as the result of the strategy. Therefore, in this phase what needs to be designed are **digital marketing roadmap**. it is important for El Primero to draw up a clear roadmap within one year of digital marketing activities that is efficient to carry out at a predetermined time. This preparation requires good consideration of the moments that will occur every year, digital marketing objectives, and the resources that will be involved. The other one is **Key Performance Index**. KPIs are very important for maintaining the objectives of digital marketing activities to keep them on track. KPI is also an indicator for evaluating effective activities to be continued or needs to be terminated due to their efficiency. All strategies and tactics that have been prepared refer to the objectives set out in objective settings phase. Therefore, KPIs that can be made collectively for all digital marketing activities are:

Table VII. KPIs of Digital Marketing

Objective	Key Performance Index
Brand awareness in digital platform	Increase the number of interactions (visit, follow, and contact from the platform) digital pages of the El Primero platform by 30% every month for the next 6 months.
Community relationship	Build relationships and involve with 5 communities every month for 2023

E. CONCLUSIONS

The main problem with El Primero Cafe & Meet's low level of brand awareness is due to the absence of an optimal and strategic digital marketing strategy. This is because the focus of El Primero's marketing activities has not yet led to digital marketing, so the impact given is that the presence of this brand in the digital world is still considered at a low level. El Primero Cafe & Meet can increase their brand awareness level by developing a community-based digital marketing strategy. This concept aims to put the brand's position with the market and community on digital platforms to increase the closeness between the market and the brand. This strategy also gives El Primero an additional presence on a digital platform so that more and more online markets are aware of the existence of this brand. For the perfection of the strategies and in line with the concept of this brand, El Primero can implement consists of many optimizations and activities that target not only one market segmentation. This community-based digital marketing activity carries out more collaborative activities and engagement processes to interact with the community, influencers, and the end market to create a collaborative climate and recommend behavior to one another.

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